

Induction of Systemic acquired resistance in Mungbean against Mungbean Yellow Mosaic Begomovirus by the exogenous application of Salicylic acid and Benzothiadiazole.

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Abstract— The diseases caused by bipartite Begomoviruses have emerged as overwhelming problem in various cropping systems of Pakistan. The study was conducted to evaluate the potential of induced resistance in mungbean to Mungbean yellow mosaic virus (MYMV) disease. In this work, resistance to MYMV infection was induced in mungbean plants by activating the Salicylic acid (SA) pathway using SA and Benzothiadiazole (BTH) as treatments. The resistance was characterized by evaluating symptom appearance and virus titer through ELISA. Elicitors i.e., SA and BTH were applied at different concentrations to enhance the innate resistance of mungbean by the induction of defense related compounds. All treatments were helpful in reducing plant infection but the most effective treatment was the combination of SA@5mM and BTH@150mg/L as compared to virus inoculated control. Three weeks analysis showed peak accumulation of defense related enzymatic antioxidants and phenols in the mungbean leaves treated with SA and BTH. Higher enzymatic activity was observed in elicitor treated plants followed by inoculation with MYMV. As the resistance increased due to the application of SA & BTH the enzymatic activities of SOD, POD, and CAT were also increased during second week after application of elicitors. This study revealed that SA and BTH are potential source for management of MYMV by enhancing the level of protection through induction of systemic acquired resistance.

Keywords— Induced resistance, *Vigna radiata*, enzymatic antioxidants, PAL, SOD, and POD.

I. INTRODUCTION

The mungbean (*Vigna radiata* L) is also called mung, green gram is dominant legume crop grown throughout the world for its edible seed and sprouts. Ninety percent of world mungbean is cultivated in Asia. In Pakistan mungbean is grown over an area of 133 thousand hectares with annual yield of 102 thousand tons. (Government of Pakistan, 2015). Grain legumes are rich source of protein contents throughout south Asia, but they are affected by a number of pest and diseases and which resulted high yield losses and among them Mungbean Yellow Mosaic virus is very devastating disease during summer months in Pakistan and more than 50% yield losses were reported in mungbean. MYMV belongs to family *Geminiviridae* and genus *Begomovirus* (Boss, 1999). Whitefly (*Bemisia tabacai*) as a vector is responsible for transmission of this virus. According to an estimate more than US\$ 300 million loss occurred due to this virus in different leguminous crops (Varma *et al.*, 1992). Initial symptoms of disease arises on foliage in the form of small intermingle green and lemon color dots on young leaves that scattered on other leaves, puckering of leaves occurred and apex of growing areas are reduced in size and irregular light green and yellow specks appear on affected leaves. (Narini, 1960). If plants are attacked at seedling stage than 100% yield losses occurred (Usharani *et al.*, 2004). These alterations emerging from disease causing organism may interrupt plant physiology and increase plant senescence and activate the defense mechanism. Systemic acquired resistance (SAR) is a phenomenon which operates in plants under stress conditions and plant produce chemicals like salicylic acid (SA), Methyl Jasmonate (MeJ) a derivative of Jasmonic acid (JS) which act as signaling hormone and provide pathway for the activation

of defense reaction. Exogenous application of SA enhances tolerance to stress, depending on the developmental phase of plants. SA is an endogenous regulator has definite role in defense mechanism against biotic and abiotic stress. Benzothiadiazole (BTH) shares the property of activating the systemic acquired resistance pathway downstream from the SA signaling. As a result of defense reaction different type of proteins known as pathogenesis related proteins (PR), phenolic compounds, reactive oxygen species (ROS) and enzymatic and non enzymatic antioxidants are produced which detoxify the reactive oxygen species produced by plant- pathogen interaction and protect plant from oxidative damage. Furthermore these compounds could be acts as biochemical markers to evaluate the developing resistance. Therefore an attempt was made for enhancing resistance against MBYMV by the exogenous application of SA and BTH. The resistance was characterized by evaluating symptom developed by viral infection, phenolic contents and enzymatic antioxidants like Superoxide dismutase (SOD), Peroxidase (POD), Catalase (CAT) and Phenylalanine ammonialyase (PAL). Application of plants with signaling molecules decrease enzyme activities and results in induction of resistance. Application of Salicylic acid and BTH results in activation of plant defense mechanism and induces resistance in plant against pathogens Salicylic acid is produced naturally in plant it is phenolic compound which is produced in plant in stress or when they are attacked by pathogen it activates signal transduction pathway and induces local and systemic resistance to pathogens (Delaney *et al.*, 1995 and Maleck *et al.*, 2000).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Induction of resistance in mungbean against MYMV

Research trial was conducted under controlled conditions to study induction of resistance in mungbean against Mungbean yellow mosaic virus (MYMV). For this purpose highly susceptible variety of mungbean i.e Kabuli mung was sown in earthen pots of 35cm filled with sand, peat and loam. The pots were irrigated daily. After 20 days of sowing when leaves become mature, plants were divided on the basis of treatments. Each treatment contained 3 replications. Plants were treated exogenously with Salicylic acid (SA) and Benzothiadiazole (BTH) (Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA) at different concentrations. After 24 hours of application mungbean plants were inoculated with viruliferous whiteflies (*Bemisia tabaci*) reared on MYMV infected plants. The inoculated plants without application of elicitor were used as infected control while plants sprayed with water were used as healthy control. The enzymatic activates i.e., PAL, POD, SOD, CAT and total Phenolic contents were determined after first, second and third week of post inoculation. The disease severity on each plant was calculated on the basis of symptoms using disease rating scale. For the detection of virus titer all the treated plant were tested through DAS-ELISA (Clark and Adam, 1977) using Tomato Yellow Leaf Curl Gemini virus polyclonal antibodies (AC, Diagnostics, USA) and has cross reactivity with other Gemini viruses.

TABLE 1
TREATMENTS APPLIED FOR MANAGEMENT OF MYMV UNDER CONTROLLED CONDITIONS

Treatments		
No.	Treatment	Treatment detail
1	T ₀	Inoculated control
2	T ₁	Healthy Control (Plants sprayed with water only)
3	T ₂	MYMV + 5mM Salicylic acid
4	T ₃	MYMV + 10mM Salicylic acid
5	T ₄	MYMV + 150mg/ L BTH
6	T ₅	MYMV+ 300 mg /L BTH
7	T ₆	MYMV+ 5mM Salicylic acid + 150 mg/ L BTH

MYMV= Mungbean yellow mosaic virus, mM= mili mole, BTH= Benzothiadiazole, mg= mili gram, L = liter

2.2 Enzyme Extraction

The activities of POD, SOD, and CAT in mungbean leaves were assayed according to the method following method. Three leaves samples of 0.2 g FW were collected from each treatment at 7, 14 and 21dpi and grinded in liquid nitrogen with the help of pestle and mortar. 2ml of 50mm ice -cold phosphate buffer (pH 7.8) containing 1mM ethylene diamine teraacetic acid

(EDTA) was added and homogenized. The mixture was Centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 15 min at 4°C. The supernatant was used as enzyme extract.

2.3 Superoxide dismutase (SOD) assay (EC 1.5.1.1)

The SOD activity is defined as the inhibition of the photochemical reduction of nitroblue tetrazolium (NBT) at 560 nm. The monitoring of this inhibits the is used to assay SOD activity. The reaction mixture was prepared by taking 50µL enzyme extract and adding 1 mL NBT (50µM), 500 µL methionine (13mM), 1mL riboflavin(1.3µM), 950µL (50mM) phosphate buffer and 500µL EDTA (75mM).This reactions was started by keeping reaction solution under 30 W fluorescent lamp illuminations and turning the flourecent lamp on.The rections stopped when the lamp turned of 5 minutes lettere. The NBT photo reduction produced blue formazane which was used to measure the increase in absorbance at 560 nm . The same reaction mixtures without enzyme extract in dark were used as blank . The SOD activity was determined and expressed as SOD IU min⁻¹ mg⁻¹ protein (Glannopolitls and Ries, 1997).

2.4 Peroxidase (POD) assay (EC 1.11.1.7)

The POD activity assayed by guaiacol oxidation and defined as 0.01 absorbance change min-1mg-1 protein. The reaction mixture was prepared by adding 400 µL guaiacol (20 mM), 500 µL H₂O₂ (40 mM) and 2mL phosphate (50mM) in 100 µL enzyme extract.The change in absorbance at 470 nm of the reaction mixture was observed every 20s up to 5min.The POD activity expressed as m.mol min⁻¹ mg protein⁻¹ (Castillo *et al.*, 1984).

2.5 Catalase (CAT) assay (EC 1.11.1.6)

The CAT activity assayed by the decomposition of H₂O₂ and change in absorbance due to H₂O₂ was obseved every 30s for 5 minutes using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. Reaction mixture for CAT contained 900µL H₂O₂ (5.9 mM) and 2mL phosphate buffer (50mM). Reaction was started by adding 100µL enzyme extract to the reaction mixture. The Catalase activity was expressed as µmol of H₂O₂ min mg⁻¹ protein⁻¹(Aebi, 1984).

2.6 PAL (Phenylalanine ammonia Lyase) activity (EC 4.3.1.24)

Leaf samples (0.5 g) were homogenized in 1200 µl of ice cold 0.1 M sodium borate buffer, pH 7, containing 1.4 mM of 2-merceptoethanol and 0.1 g of insoluble polyvenylpyrrolidone. The extract was filtered through cheese cloth and the filtrate was centrifuged at 14,000 rpm at 4° C for 15 minutes. The supernatant was used as enzyme source. PAL activity was determined as the rate of conversion of L-phenylalanine to trans-cinnamic acid at 290 nm asdescribed by Dickerson *et al.* (1984). Sample containing 0.4 mL of enzyme extract was incubated with 0.5 mL of o.1 M borate buffer, pH 8.8 and 0.5 mL of 12 mM L- phenylalanine in the same buffer for 30 minutes at 40° C. The amount of trans-cinnamic acid synthesized was calculated using its extinction coefficient of 9630 m⁻¹ (Dickerson *et al.*, 1984). Enzyme activity was expressed as nmol trans-cinnamic acid min⁻¹ mg⁻¹ protein

2.7 Estimation of total phenolic contents (EC 1.14.13.7)

Total phenols of leaf samples were determined at 760 nm using gallic acid as reference standard (Ainsworth and gillespie, 2007). To create calibration curve the standard solution were prepared in different concentration i.e. 500, 250, 150 and 100 mg L⁻¹ gallic acid. For extraction and preparation of sample, 0.5 g leaf sample was homogenized in 5 ml acetone (80%). Filtration followed by extraction and volume of filtrate was raised with acetone upto 10 ml. Then reaction mixture was prepared by taking 20 µL sample or standard and adding 1.58 ml water, 100 µL Follin-ciocalteu reagent within 30 seconds upto 8 minutes. Reaction mixture was left at 40°C for 30 minutes or at 25 °C for 120 minutes after adding and mixing 300 µL sodium carbonate. Absorbance of reaction mixture was read at 760 nm against the blank (80% acetone). Total phenol level in samples were determined by plotting calibration curve from standards and reported as gallic acid equivalent GAE.

Total protein estimation was carried out by Bradford assay (Bradford, 1976).

2.8 Statistical analysis

Data was subjected to statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA) using (Statistical software package 8.0 Institute Carry Inc; USA). Treatment means were compared using Fisher's least significant differences (LSD) at ($P = 0.05$).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the trial revealed that all the treatments have significantly help in reducing the disease severity as compared to the control. Disease severity of MYMV with respect to each treatment was shown in figure.1. The maximum disease

suppression was observed as compared to infected control where the treatments of SA@ 5 mM and BTH @150 mgL⁻¹ were applied with the disease severity ranged between 14% and 13.8% as compared to infected control where it was up to 45%.

3.1 Phenylalanine ammonia lyase (PAL) activity assay

The enzymatic activities after the induction of resistance through elicitors against MYMV were increased significantly as compared to both the virus infected and healthy controls. The PAL activity was increased in all the treatments significantly as compared to infected and healthy controls (Fig.2) Maximum PAL activity was observed in first week after application of treatment of SA@ 5mM + virus followed by 10mM S.A + virus . PAL activities tend to decreased after every week.

3.2 Peroxidase (POD) activity assay

The POD activity was increased in all treatments after application as compared to infected and healthy controls (Fig.3). During three weeks after application maximum POD activity was observed in second week on the treatment of SA@5mM + virus.

3.3 Superoxide dismutase (SOD) assay

There was significant effect of S.A and BTH on SOD activity in second and third week after treatments as compared to the controls. In first week after application of treatments the SOD activity was very low but in second week, it was increased and remained almost at higher level. Where the SOD activity in BTH + virus treated plants was decreased in third week.

3.4 Catalase (CAT) activity assay

The CAT activity was greatly increased in second week after application. The most effective treatment which showed maximum CAT activity was SA @10mM + virus and BTH @150mg/ L+ virus. The CAT activity was tend to decreased after in third week.

3.5 Total phenolic contents assay

Total phenolic contents were increased significantly as compared to the healthy and inoculated controls. The effect of treatments on the production of total phenolic contents remained almost same during all three weeks after applications. Total phenolic contents were maximum in third week in all treated plants.

IV. DISCUSSION

There was scarcity of resistant genetic source in mungbean, so innate defense of plant was enhanced by exogenous application of Salicylic acid and benzothiadiazole under controlled conditions on highly susceptible cultivar of mungbean. Salicylic acid (SA) is natural plant hormone which is responsible in natural plant defense mechanism in response to pathogen attack and this signaling molecule is helpful in induction of resistance in plants. In case of lack of natural defense mechanism of plants, exogenous treatment of elicitor like SA (salicylic acid) and BTH (Benzothiadiazole) are helpful in the induction of resistance in plants. Enzymatic antioxidants are produced in plants and played an important role in induced systemic acquired resistance, furthermore acts as a biochemical markers to evaluate the developing resistance as the result of elicitor application in plants. Ashry and Mohamed, (2011) reported the increased activities of POD and CAT enzymes in *Tomato yellow leaf curl virus* (TYLCV) infected leaves and induce resistance in the host plant. Induced resistance in plants may increases the ability of susceptible plants to withstand pathogens in a non-genetic way (Kagale, *et al*, 2004). As it is reported that the induced resistance prior to challenge infection elevates the level of some defense compounds and sensitizes the plants to rapidly produce some compounds after infection and thereby, provide protection against the disease (Biswas, *et al.*, 2012). The phenomenon of induced resistance may involve the production of pathogenesis related proteins and antioxidative enzymes etc. Kagale, *et al.* (2011) reported that elicitor applications involve induction of systemic resistance by the activation of various defense-related enzymes POD and PAL. The elevated level of these enzymes may be involved in the protection of the host plant against systemic infection. This is in agreement with the previous findings that the increased level of phenolics could provide an adequate substrate to oxidative reactions catalyzed by POD make the medium unfavorable to the further development of pathogens, (Lattanzio, *et al.*, 2006). Our study was similar to the findings of Radwan *et al.* , (2006) who studied the application of SA on cucumber and pumpkin infected by *Zucchini yellow mosaic virus* (ZYMV) and the resultant

enzymatic activity of PAL, POD, CAT and SOD activity were increased by three folds by application of SA. Our findings are also similar to findings of Loon (1989) who concluded that when plant is in stress by environmental factors or pathogen attack than a variety of pathogenesis related proteins are accumulated in plants that provide resistance to plant. POD can oxidize phenolic compounds into antimicrobial quinones, which inhibit viruses by inactivating viral DNA and RNA (Lamb and Dixon, 1997). Elbadry *et al.* (2006) suggested that external application of SA was helpful in providing systemic acquired resistance against *Bean yellow mosaic virus* (BYMV) in faba beans by enhancing production of oxidative enzymes. Siddique *et al.*, (2014) result revealed that SOD, CAT, PAL, POD, Phenolic contents and proteins played vital role in defense mechanism of cotton plant against CLCuBuV. This finding suggested that correlation exist between integral extent of enzymes activities and resistance of plant and acts as biochemical markers for analyzing compatible and incompatible plant-virus relationship. External application of SA in appropriate concentration significantly reduce systemic infection of MYMV before inoculation and no prominent symptom of MYMV was observed at 100 μ M concentration of SA (Kundu *et al.*, 2011). Primary and secondary metabolism was depended on enhanced protein synthesis during metabolic reprogramming which is very important for induction of resistance by SA against MYMV. Recognition of proteins depicting huge profusion, associated with process of photosynthesis is essential analysis which recovers virus induced destruction of photosynthesis process and gave increased metabolites that are needed for re distribution of available defense resources. Our findings are in agreement with Mandal, (2010). Elicitors are efficient and imitate in recognition of pest by plants, hence activate the delicate and easy defense capability in plants. Activity of PAL by application of SA, and BTH showed an increase in POD activity was increased. The effect or activity of these compounds on other antioxidants like CAT, SOD were also higher by these elicitors. Phenolics deposition and activity of several defense enzymes were increased as they were triggered by elicitor. SA application is helpful in activation of defense proteins in plants (Clarke *et al.*, 1998). The results of this investigation suggested that when SA was applied to plants infested with viruses than Pathogenesis related proteins (PR) inhibit production of viral replication and movement protein. Ashfaq *et al.* (2010) also observed that when viral pathogen attacked on Urdbean (*Vigna mungo* L.) plant then total proteins were increased due to viral proteins. It has been known for some time that SA modulates the induction of SAR following pathogen attack (Neuenschwander *et al.*, 1996; Ryals *et al.*, 1996) Loon *et al.* (1994) concluded that PR proteins has strong defense ability against viral infection. In our whole study on induction of resistance in highly susceptible variety Kabuli mung under controlled conditions we observed that by application of elicitor compounds BTH and SA activity of defense related antioxidants like SOD, POD, PAL, CAT and total proteins and phenolic contents were higher in mungbean leaves that were treated with elicitor compounds and in healthy control as compared to infected control our study coincides with investigation of many scientists their results also showed that the external application of elicitor molecules enhances plant defense system by producing higher level of SOD, POD, CAT, phenols and proteins. The most appropriate defense mechanism of plants was linked with metabolic variation that are integrated in plants and Socheath Ong and Filomena, (2016) findings are interconnected with our results in their results leaf curl infection in tomato plant was reduced by application of SA and activities of SOD, POD, CAT was increased in treated plants as compared to infected control. Our results are linked with the study that SA and BTH application significantly increases oxidative enzymes accumulation in Tobacco plant infected with *Tobacco mosaic virus* (TMV) (Zechmann *et al.*, 2003). The generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) is one of the initial responses of plants to pathogens (Mehdy, 1994; Vanacker *et al.*, 2000). As a major scavenger in antioxidant enzyme systems that protect cellular membranes and organelles from AOS in plants, SOD converts superoxide anion radicals to hydrogen peroxide and oxygen by disproportion (Fridovich, 1986). PAL, a key enzyme in phenylpropanoid metabolism, plays a significant role in the synthesis of various secondary metabolites (e.g., phenols, phenylpropanoids, and lignin and salicylic acid monomers) that are involved in plant immunity and induce resistance by PGPR (Gerasimova *et al.*, 2005; Harish *et al.*, 2008). The accumulation of these secondary metabolites was thought to restrict virus invasion (Lian *et al.*, 2011). BTH-treated *Arabidopsis thaliana* plants were described as resistant to infection by *turnip crinkle virus*, *Pseudomonas syringae* pv 'tomato' DC3000 and *Peronospora parasitica* (Lawton *et al.*, 1996). Treatment of mungbean plants with BTH and SA reduced the percentage of infected plants and the plants that became infected displayed less severe symptoms. The reduction was directly correlated with the concentration of BTH and SA and the time period between application and the inoculation with the virus.

V. CONCLUSIONS

It is concluded that an exogenous application of SA and BTH could offer a good source of the management of MYMV by inducing resistance in highly susceptible of mung bean.

FIG. 1. DISEASE SEVERITY OF MYMV IN GLASS HOUSE WITH RESPECT TO TREATMENTS

FIG. 2. PAL ACTIVITY WITH RESPECT TO DAYS AFTER APPLICATION OF ELICITORS

FIG. 3. POD ACTIVITY WITH RESPECT TO DAYS AFTER APPLICATION OF ELICITORS

FIG. 4. SOD ACTIVITY WITH RESPECT TO DAYS AFTER APPLICATION OF ELICITORS PROTEIN

FIG. 5. CAT ACTIVITY WITH RESPECT TO DAYS AFTER APPLICATION OF ELICITOR

FIG. 6. TOTAL PHENOLIC CONTENTS WITH RESPECT TO DAYS AFTER APPLICATION OF ELICITORS

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